

Kontaktsiz kuchlanish relelari asosida reaktiv quvvatni boshqarishni modellashtirish usullari

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Dolzarblik: Sanoat korxonalarida reaktiv quvvatni samarali boshqarish muammosi, yuqori energiya iste'moli, texnik yo'qotishlar va iqtisodiy zararlar bilan bog'liq holda, juda dolzarb hisoblanadi. Ayniqsa, Vazirlar Mahkamasi huzuridagi inspeksiya tomonidan reaktiv quvvatni ortiqcha iste'mol qilganlik uchun jarimalar joriy etilayotgani bu masalani yanada muhimlashtirmoqda. Sabr vaqti boshqariladigan kontaktsiz kuchlanish relelari asosida avtomatik boshqaruv tizimini shakllantirish va uning samaradorligini mashinani o'qitish, genetik algoritmlar va Fuzzy mantig'i asosida tahlil qilish, real vaqt rejimida aniq va tezkor boshqaruvni ta'minlashga xizmat qiladi. Ayniqsa, ikkinchi tur Fuzzy boshqaruv usuli sanoatdagi dinamik va noaniq jarayonlarni hisobga olishda yuqori samaradorlikka ega bo'lib, zamonaviy intellektual energetik boshqaruvni joriy etish imkonini yaratadi. Shu boisdan tadqiqot natijalari amaliyot uchun katta ilmiy va iqtisodiy ahamiyatga ega.

Maqsad: Sanoat korxonalarida reaktiv quvvatni sabr vaqti boshqariladigan kontaktsiz kuchlanish relelari asosida intellektual usullar yordamida avtomatik boshqarish modelini ishlab chiqish, zamonaviy algoritmlar (mashinani o'qitish, genetik algoritmlar, Fuzzy mantig'i) asosida boshqaruv samaradorligini baholash va noaniqlikni optimal tarzda kamaytirishdan iborat.

Usullar: Tadqiqotda mashinani o'qitish, chuqur o'qish, genetik algoritmlar va Fuzzy mantig'i kabi intellektual usullar qo'llanildi. Ushbu usullar yordamida reaktiv quvvatni boshqarish modellari yaratildi, tahlil qilindi va ularning samaradorligi, noaniqlikni boshqarish qobiliyati hamda avtomatik boshqaruvdagi rollari baholandi.

Natijalar: Tadqiqot natijasida reaktiv quvvatni boshqarishda Fuzzy mantig'i, ayniqsa uning ikkinchi turi, eng samarali usul ekanligi aniqlandi. Mashinani o'qitish va chuqur o'qish usullari yuqori aniqlikka ega ekanligi tasdiqlandi, biroq ular "qora quti" tabiati va katta hisoblash resurslariga ehtiyoj tufayli cheklovlarga ega. Genetik algoritmlar universal va moslashuvchan bo'lsa-da, doimiy optimal yechimni ta'minlay olmasligi mumkin. Fuzzy mantig'i real hayotdagi noaniqlikni to'liq qamrab olib, tezkor va ishonchli boshqaruvni amalga oshirish imkonini berdi.

Kalit so'zlar: Reaktiv quvvat, kontaktsiz kuchlanish relesi, sabr vaqti boshqaruv, mashinani o'qitish, chuqur o'rganish, genetik algoritmlar, Fuzzy mantig'i, avtomatik boshqaruv, intellektual nazorat, sanoat energetika tizimi, noaniqlikni boshqarish.

Моделирование методов управления реактивной мощностью с использованием бесконтактных реле напряжения

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Актуальность: Проблема эффективного управления реактивной мощностью на промышленных предприятиях является крайне актуальной в связи с высоким потреблением энергии, техническими потерями и экономическим ущербом. Особенно важным данный вопрос становится в условиях введения штрафов Инспекцией при Кабинете Министров за превышение установленного лимита потребления реактивной мощности. Формирование автоматической системы управления на основе бесконтактных реле напряжения с регулируемым временем срабатывания и анализ её эффективности с использованием методов машинного обучения, генетических алгоритмов и нечеткой логики (Fuzzy logic) позволяет обеспечить точное и оперативное управление в реальном времени. Особенно эффективной является система управления второго типа на основе нечеткой логики, учитывающая динамические и неопределённые процессы в промышленности. Поэтому результаты данного исследования имеют

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высокую научную и практическую значимость.

Цель: Разработка модели автоматического управления реактивной мощностью на промышленных предприятиях с использованием интеллектуальных методов на основе бесконтактных реле напряжения с регулируемым временем срабатывания, а также оценка эффективности управления на базе современных алгоритмов (машинное обучение, генетический алгоритм, нечеткая логика) и оптимальное уменьшение неопределённости.

Методы: В исследовании были применены интеллектуальные методы, такие как машинное обучение, глубокое обучение, генетические алгоритмы и нечеткая логика. С их помощью были разработаны и проанализированы модели управления реактивной мощностью, а также оценены их эффективность, способность управления неопределённостью и роль в автоматическом управлении.

Результаты: В результате исследования было установлено, что наиболее эффективным методом управления реактивной мощностью является нечеткая логика (Fuzzy logic), особенно её второй тип. Методы машинного и глубокого обучения продемонстрировали высокую точность, однако их "чёрный ящик" характер и высокая требовательность к вычислительным ресурсам создают определённые ограничения. Генетические алгоритмы универсальны и адаптивны, но не всегда гарантируют нахождение оптимального решения. Нечеткая логика охватывает неопределённости реальной жизни и обеспечивает быстрое и надёжное управление.

Ключевые слова: Реактивная мощность, бесконтактное реле напряжения, управление временем срабатывания, машинное обучение, глубокое обучение, генетические алгоритмы, нечеткая логика, автоматическое управление, интеллектуальный контроль, энергетическая система промышленности, управление неопределённостью.

Modeling approaches for reactive power control using contactless voltage relays

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Relevance: The issue of efficient reactive power management in industrial enterprises is highly relevant due to high energy consumption, technical losses, and economic damages. This problem has become even more critical with the implementation of penalties by the Inspection under the Cabinet of Ministers for exceeding the allowed limits of reactive power consumption. Establishing an automatic control system based on contactless voltage relays with adjustable delay time and analyzing its efficiency through machine learning, genetic algorithms, and fuzzy logic ensures accurate and rapid control in real-time. In particular, the second-type fuzzy logic control system demonstrates high efficiency in managing dynamic and uncertain industrial processes. Therefore, the findings of this research have significant scientific and practical importance.

Aim: The development of an automatic control model for reactive power management in industrial enterprises using intelligent methods based on contactless voltage relays with adjustable delay time, along with evaluating control efficiency through modern algorithms (machine learning, genetic algorithm, fuzzy logic) and optimally reducing uncertainty.

Methods: The study employed intelligent methods such as machine learning, deep learning, genetic algorithms, and fuzzy logic. Using these methods, reactive power control models were developed and analyzed, and their effectiveness, ability to manage uncertainty, and role in automatic control were evaluated.

Results: As a result of the study, it was determined that fuzzy logic, especially its second type, is the most effective method for reactive power control. Machine learning and deep learning methods demonstrated high accuracy, but their "black-box" nature and demand for high computational resources pose certain limitations. Genetic algorithms are universal and flexible, but they may not always guarantee an optimal solution. Fuzzy logic fully captures real-life uncertainties and enables fast and reliable control.

Keywords: Reactive power, contactless voltage relay, delay time control, machine learning, deep learning, genetic algorithms, fuzzy logic, automatic control, intelligent supervision, industrial energy system, uncertainty management.

1. Introduction

In the power supply systems of industrial enterprises, improper management of reactive power consumption leads to excessive reactive power flow within the networks. According to the resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the regulation of electricity, petroleum products, and gas consumption, if reactive power consumption exceeds the prescribed limits or is transferred to the grid, a penalty equal to three times the current tariff for each kilowatt of wasted active power is imposed. By analyzing the demand for reactive power and intelligently managing reactive power sources through smart systems, it becomes possible to prevent excessive reactive power from flowing into the electrical network, avoid active energy losses in the grid, and reduce technical-technological and economic damages caused by such inefficiencies. This article sets forth the development of an effective model for reactive power management using modern methods based on non-contact voltage relays with controllable time delay and evaluates its efficiency. The study analyzes current advanced methods applied in the intelligent management of reactive power, particularly those based on machine learning, deep learning, genetic algorithms, and fuzzy logic [1-4].

2. Materials and Methods

Today, intelligent control of reactive power is increasingly implemented using these methods. However, each method has its own specific features, and selecting the most optimal approach depends significantly on the automatic control strategy and its control parameters. Among the various methods of machine learning, linear control is one of the fundamental approaches, which is implemented as follows [3]:

$$y = \omega_0 + \omega_1 x_1 + \omega_2 x_2 + \dots + \omega_n x_n$$

where, y – output result (predicted value from the model), x_i – input features, ω_i – weight coefficients of the learned parameters.

In this case, the control model is implemented based on minimizing the error to achieve the least possible prediction error.

$$J(\omega) = \frac{1}{m} \sum_{i=1}^m (y_i - y'_i)^2$$

$J(\omega)$ – error function

y_i – real values

y'_i – values calculated by the model

m – number of data

of the weight coefficient is determined as follows:

$$\omega_j := \omega_j - \alpha \frac{\partial}{\partial \omega_j} J(\omega)$$

α – learning rate

ω_j – value of model parameters

$\alpha \frac{\partial}{\partial \omega_j} J(\omega)$ is the degree of the error function

Based on the above sequence, a machine learning model is developed and applied to the control process.

Deep learning is an extension of machine learning based on multi-layer neural networks, offering the ability to model complex relationships by identifying intricate patterns within data. There are several methods of deep learning, with the primary approach for calculating the output value expressed as follows [5]:

$$y = f\left(\sum_{i=1}^n \omega_i x_i + b\right)$$

y – is the output value of the neuron

x_i – input values

ω_i – weight coefficients i

b – shift coefficient (bias)

$f(\cdot)$ – activation function (for example, sigmoid , ReLU or tanh)

The sigmoid function is one of the activation functions that determines the learning method [6]:

$$f(x) = \frac{1}{1 + e^{-x}}$$

or ReLU function :

$$f(x) = \max(0, x)$$

The control model is developed in stages, passing through three main layers: input, hidden, and output (Figure 1). Depending on the problem, re-learning is carried out either directly or by going back.

Fig.1. A general architecture of deep learning

In this case, the basic expression of general management is as follows:

$$\delta^{(L)} = \nabla_a J \odot f'(z^{(L)})$$

$\delta^{(L)}$ – errors in the output layer

J is a general error function

$f'(z^{(L)})$ is the derivative of the activation function

\odot – multiplication by elements

Backward calculation of errors for the intermediate layer is performed as follows :

$$\delta^{(l)} = ((\omega^{(l+1)})^T \delta^{(l+1)}) \odot f'(z^{(l)})$$

$\delta^{(l)}$ – errors in the intermediate layer

$\omega^{(l+1)}$ – the weight coefficient of the next layer

$f'(z^{(l)})$ is the derivative of the activation function in the intermediate layer

The transition vases from each layer are updated using the following formula:

$$\omega_{ij}^{(l)} := \omega_{ij}^{(l)} + \alpha \frac{\partial J}{\partial \omega_{ij}^{(l)}} \quad b_j^{(l)} := b_j^{(l)} + \alpha \frac{\partial J}{\partial \omega_j^{(l)}}$$

α – learning speed

$\frac{\partial J}{\partial \omega_{ij}^{(l)}}$, $\frac{\partial J}{\partial \omega_j^{(l)}}$ – gradients of error in terms of severity and bias

Modeling automatic control through deep learning is done by properly choosing the hyperparameters of the neural network.

Genetic Algorithms are also a modern solution for automatic control, and are a computational method used to model complex controls. They are similar to biological evolution and operate on the principles of natural selection and evolution, based on the basic algorithm shown in Figure 2 [7].

In control modeling, a function that evaluates the quality of each solution is developed, and its main expression is as follows:

$$F(x) \rightarrow \max \text{ yoki } \min$$

$F(x)$ – fitness function.

x – the solution in the population (chromosome).

In selection, the selection of the best solutions based on probability is carried out as follows (roulette wheel selection):

$$P_i = \frac{F(x_i)}{\sum_{j=1}^N F(x_j)}$$

Here:

P_i – the probability of choosing the i -th chromosome.

$F(x_i)$ – fitness value of solution i .

N – population size.

Next in phase selection through good new solutions to the next generation will be held. K ros s over (cutting work) two father - mother solutions through new create solution (child). process considered, mainly as follows is expressed as [8]:

Single point cutting. If there are two parental chromosomes:

$$P_1 = [x_1, x_2, x_3, \dots, x_n], P_2 = [y_1, y_2, y_3, \dots, y_n]$$

The child chromosomes (C) are generated as follows: The crossover point (k) is chosen randomly and the following formula is used :

$$C = [x_1, x_2, x_3, \dots, x_k, y_{k+1}, \dots, y_n], 1 \leq k \leq n$$

Another option (mixed method):

$$C = \alpha \cdot P_1 + (1 - \alpha) \cdot P_2, 1 \leq k \leq n$$

α – a randomly selected parameter.

Mutation random chosen solution one or one how many points change through new What are the solutions ? creates Random chosen point change as follows to do increases :

$$x'_i = x_i + \epsilon$$

where ϵ is a small random value (change amplitude).

Fig. 2. Basic algorithm of genetic algorithm

This method is an effective solution for automatic control of a complete process in automatic control with historical data with high accuracy and low variability.

Fuzzy logic is used to model processes that, unlike machine learning and deep learning and genetic algorithm models, do not operate on the basis of specific rules and are controlled solely by human experience. In this method of modeling, a set of fuzzy rules, fuzzification and defuzzification are carried out by developing a membership function. In it, a membership function is first developed and, based on the nature of the process controlled by it, it is modeled as follows:

$$\mu_A(x): X \rightarrow [0,1]$$

Here:

X – a collection of objects

A – fuzzy set

$\mu_A(x)$ – level of object belonging to the set (value between 0 and 1)

Modeling begins with the process of converting a precise value into a fuzzy value:

$$\mu_A(x^*) \quad (\text{aniq qiymat } x^* \text{ uchun})$$

The rules of fuzzy logic simulation are expressed in the following form:

$$\text{IF } x \text{ is } A \text{ THEN } y \text{ is } B$$

Here:

x – input variable

y – exit price

A and B – fuzzy sets.

The most commonly used method for obtaining the general result of fuzzy rules is the Mamdani method . If there are two rules, for example:

$$\text{IF } x \text{ is } A_1, \text{ THEN } y \text{ is } B_1$$

$$\text{IF } x \text{ is } A_2, \text{ THEN } y \text{ is } B_2$$

Then the output value is summarized by the following formula:

$$\mu_{B'}(y) = \max [\min (\mu_{A_1}(x), \mu_{B_1}(y)), \min (\mu_{A_2}(x), \mu_{B_2}(y))]]$$

Here:

$\mu_{A_1}(x), \mu_{B_1}(y)$ - degree of affiliation of input values;

$\mu_{A_2}(x), \mu_{B_2}(y)$ - output membership function values.

Defuzzification is the process of converting a fuzzy result back to a precise numerical form, which gives the resulting output value. The following formula is often used (center of gravity method):

$$y^* = \frac{\int \mu_B(y) \cdot y dy}{\int \mu_B(y) dy}$$

Here:

y - exit price.

$\mu_B(y)$ - the final fuzzy set membership value.

3. Results

There are a number of advantages and disadvantages in applying the above methods to controlling multiple reactive power through non-contact voltage relays with tolerance time control. These methods were studied and the resulting table presented in Table 1 was created [9-12].

Table 1. Used in the organization of management analytical table of the most optimal methods

No.	Method name	Advantage	Disadvantage	Areas of application
1	Machine learning and deep reading	adaptability automation of complex control systems	information dependence black box nature resource demand	recognize the picture natural language processing analytics independent systems
2	Genetic algorithms	optimization adaptability multifacetedness	calculation requirement lack of precision not always finding the exact optimal solution sensitivity to parameters	planning design setting machine read parameters robotics
3	Fuzzy logic	uncertainty and uncertainty management intuitive decision making adaptability	design and implementation complexity subjectivity in rule accuracy	management systems implementation of management by making decisions industrial and consumer management

The results of the analysis in Table 1 show that *Fuzzy logic* is the most effective method for this research object. There are two types of control mechanisms in *fuzzy logic* control:

4. Discussion

1. First round
2. Second round

The main difference between the first and second type of fuzzy systems of control mechanisms is manifested in the fuzzification process they use and the structure and complexity of the membership (membership) functions. The first type of fuzzy control mechanism is based on traditional fuzzy logic, in which the degree of belonging of each element to the fuzzy set is determined by a unique value. In such systems, the membership value is expressed as a definite number between 0 and 1, (Fig. 3). [13]

Fig. 3. The first type of control mechanisms

It has D_A A decision is made based on differentiation, taking into account the degree of correlation between the x -values in the data set : $\mu_x(x)$

$$A = \int_{D_x} \mu_A(x)/x$$

In the first type of fuzzy logic, the membership function is exact, strict, and definite, expressing with a single number the extent to which the value of each input variable belongs to a certain fuzzy set. In this case, for any input value, its degree of belonging to the fuzzy set is determined by a single exact number from 0 to 1, and this value itself does not have any ambiguity.

The second type of fuzzy control mechanisms is a more advanced form of the first type of fuzzy systems, in which instead of a single fixed value for the level of membership, a range of possible values or fuzzy intervals is introduced. As a result, the level of membership is characterized by its own uncertainty, uncertainty, that is, the degree of belonging of elements to fuzzy sets is also expressed in the range of fuzzy values. Through this method, the system has the opportunity to cover a wider range of uncertainties in real life and increases the reliability and accuracy of the resulting management decisions [14].

Fig. 4. The second type of control mechanisms

This approach is useful in situations where it is difficult to define the membership function precisely due to the dynamic and complex nature of the system. In such cases, instead of specifying a specific membership value for each element x introduced into the system, its membership degree is determined by a set of possible values D_x is expressed by the values in the set D_x . Then this D_x The values in the set are summarized into a more comprehensive secondary set J_x . As a result, the final decision made by the system is formed on the basis of these secondary generalized membership values,

which allows for more complete accounting of uncertainty and dynamic changes in the process [15].

$$\tilde{A} = \{((x, u), \mu_{\tilde{A}}(x, u)) | \forall x \in X; \forall u \in J_x \subseteq [0, 1]\}$$

In the quoted formula (4.2). \tilde{A} The dataset is defined as:

$$\tilde{A} = \iint_{x \in D_x, u \in J_x \subseteq [0, 1]} \frac{\mu_{\tilde{A}}(x, u)}{(x, u)} = \iint_{x \in D_x, u \in J_x \subseteq [0, 1]} \frac{1}{(x, u)} = \int_{x \in D_x} \left[\int_{u \in J_x \subseteq [0, 1]} \frac{1}{u} \right] 1/x$$

The selection process for first- and second-type control mechanisms is directly influenced by the nature of the problem at hand. This includes the system's goals and objectives, the degree of uncertainty involved in the process, and the availability of sufficient computational resources. If the uncertainty in system processes is low or moderate, and precise calculation results are feasible, then Type-1 Fuzzy control mechanisms are sufficient. However, when the process exhibits high dynamics and uncertainty, and it becomes challenging to define the membership functions precisely, it is more appropriate to use Type-2 Fuzzy systems.

The primary objective of this chapter is to introduce reactive power control systems based on non-contact voltage relays controlled by endurance time for use in industrial enterprises. Particular emphasis is placed on the optimal selection of system output parameters, considering multiple variable input parameters and their respective ranges of variation. This approach enhances system performance by effectively managing the complexity and uncertainty present in industrial environments.

5. Conclusions

Based on the study's findings, the application of intelligent methods is highly significant for effective reactive power control. Machine learning and deep learning methods offer high precision due to their reliance on large volumes of data, but their "black-box" nature and substantial computational requirements can be limiting. Genetic algorithms are flexible and adaptable, making them suitable for solving complex problems; however, they do not always guarantee optimal solutions.

Among the methods analyzed, fuzzy logic was identified as the most effective, as it is capable of accurately modeling the uncertainty and dynamic behavior of real-world processes. Specifically, Type-2 Fuzzy systems provide the highest level of control accuracy. Therefore, it is recommended to implement Type-2 Fuzzy control systems for automatic reactive power control in industrial enterprises.

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